

ISic1394

I.Sicily inscription 1394

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.04.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140901

1. Ἀπόλλωνι
2. Ἡράκ[λ]ειος
3. Ἀριστοφύλου
4. δεκυρεύσας
5. ἐκ τῶν ιδίων.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493009

EDCS 39101521

PHI 140901

Bibliography

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